

Modulos Defined with Coverings: Cauchy-Schwarz Inequality Induced Graph 덮개들로 정의된 모듈로 연산들 : 코시-슈바르츠 부등식에 점화된 그래프

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Abstract

[한글] 모듈로 연산을 무한 덮개의 성질로서 정의할 수 있다. 이러한 모듈로 군들의 확장을 코시-슈바르츠 부등식에 의거하여 그래프의 관계로 나타낼 수 있다.

[English] Modulo operations can be defined with property of infinite coverings. These expansions in modulo groups can be induced fully in relation of graphs by Cauchy-Schwarz inequality.

1 Introduction

All the notations and preconditions follow the book referenced[김성기(2011), Fraleigh and Brand(2020), Rudin(1976)]. Modulo groups can be defined with infinite coverings. And this relation can be generalized with Cauchy-Schwarz inequality.

2 Modulo: Infinite Coverings in Integer Field

There are three properties when equivalence is provided in modulo operation.

1. Reflective: equals in xRx
2. Symmetric: equals in xRy and yRx
3. Transitive: equals in if xRy and yRz then xRz

Then partition and cells are defined. With these properties, coverings in integer field can be defined.

Definition 1. (*Coverings in Integer Field*) By definition, any infinite coverings that cover integer field must have at least one element from at least one cell. With this occasion, covering can be defined with cell mapping with partition n as $\mathcal{M} : \mathbb{Z}_{mod\ n} \rightarrow \{C : C \supseteq \bigcup_i^n \bar{v}_i\}$.

This induces useful property of simple guarantee in compactness. If all the coverings can be defined with set or union set of cells, then with any interval the coverings to finite subset of integer field can be regarded as compact.

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{With } X \in \mathbb{Z}, \text{ Covering } C_{a,b,c,\dots} \text{ to set } X = \bar{a} \cap \bar{b} \cap \bar{c} \cap \dots \\ &\Rightarrow \forall X' \subset X, X' \text{ is compact with coverings } C. \end{aligned}$$

Then, arbitrary C becomes if and only if one or more possible power set(s) in cells with partition of n . Then properties of modulo equivalence can be applied in coverings also.

3 Closed Group of Graph Induced with Cauchy-Schwarz Inequality

Assuming of group \mathcal{G} within \mathbb{Z} with extended operator $a +_n b$ which was introduced in the reference[Fraleigh and Brand(2020)].

$$p +_n q \begin{cases} p + q < n \rightarrow p +_n q = p + q \\ p + q \geq n \rightarrow p +_n q = p + q - n \end{cases}$$

With $p, q \in \mathbb{R}^\nu$, and $n = \nu^2$, then $\nu \times \nu$ Cayley table can demonstrated.

$+_n$	e	a	b	c	\dots
e	e	a	b	c	\dots
a	a	b	c	d	\dots
b	b	a	c	b	\dots
c	c	a	b	d	\dots
\dots	\dots	\dots	\dots	\dots	\dots

With preceding discussion with coverings, closed group can be induced that fits Cauchy-Schwarz inequality.

$$\begin{aligned} & | \langle x, y \rangle |^2 \leq \langle x, x \rangle \cdot \langle y, y \rangle \\ \Rightarrow & | \langle (a, b, c, \dots), (d, e, f, \dots) \rangle |^2 \leq \langle (a, b, c, \dots), (a, b, c, \dots) \rangle \cdot \langle (d, e, f, \dots), (d, e, f, \dots) \rangle \end{aligned}$$

This inequality can be applied to closed residual group in same partition n . Then it becomes true to coverings also. The number of isomorphism induced with Cayley table can said to be conserved in unique number of graph in matrix. So to say in extension to coverings, arbitrary number of unique graphs $G_a, G_{a,b}, G_{a,b,c}, \dots$ in vertices a, b, c, d, e, f, \dots that conserves its isomorphism always follow the sequence of expansion:

$$\begin{aligned} & | \langle x, y \rangle |^2 \leq \langle x, x \rangle \cdot \langle y, y \rangle \\ \Rightarrow & | \langle G_{a,b,c,\dots}, G_{d,e,f,\dots} \rangle |^2 \leq \langle G_{a,b,c,\dots}, G_{a,b,c,\dots} \rangle \cdot \langle G_{d,e,f,\dots}, G_{d,e,f,\dots} \rangle \end{aligned}$$

Which in case dot product of graphs means equivalent in relation to matrix of graph. This applies same with in case of coverings to the graph also.

References

[김성기(2011)] 계승혁 김성기, 김도한. *해석개론(개정판 2판)*. September 2011.

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[Rudin(1976)] Walter Rudin. *Principles of mathematical analysis (int'l ed)*. McGraw-Hill Professional, New York, NY, 3 edition, September 1976.